

THERMO-MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE AND FATIGUE CYCLING OF NOVEL BISMALIMIDE-BASED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER RESIN AND COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Shape Memory Polymers (SMP's) have attracted great interest in recent years for application in adaptive (multi-mission) structures [1]. Compared with shape memory alloys, polymeric shape memory materials possess the advantages of high elastic deformation (strain up to more than 200% for most of the materials), low cost, low density, and potential biocompatibility and biodegradability. However, relevant aerospace and propulsion environments require materials with enhanced durability and transition temperatures well in excess of those produced for biomedical applications. With operation temperatures of subsonic structural aircraft components often reaching 121°C (250°F), it is desired that the transition temperatures of the shape memory polymers synthesized here be in excess of 121°C to ensure that shape memory polymers will not be prematurely triggered by the existing heat loads. Shape memory polymers that exhibit a glass transition temperature (T_g) greater than 120°C are uncommon among many of the current classes of previously examined thermosetting materials (epoxies, polyurethanes, and styrene copolymers) [2-7].

In recent works [8-9], a series of novel cross linked polyaspartimide-urea based polymers utilizing 4-4-bismaleimidodiphenyl-methane, a jeffamine diamine, and a bis-isocyanate were synthesized and chemically characterized. The synthesis involved coupling of the BMI with the diamine to create a linear polymer of both rigid and soft segments. The glass transition temperature and shape memory properties were varied using the diisocyanate resin creating a urea crosslinking moiety between the polyaspartimide chains. The studies by Shumaker et al. [8] and McClung et al. [9] showed that a range of T_g values from 110-164°C were possible by varying the cross-linked density of BMI-JA-400-X systems. However, it was determined [10] that the BMI-JA-

400-X resin was not processable to make composites because it did not have a pot-life (i.e., the cure reaction occurred instantly). Also, the resin viscosity at room temperature was above 200 poise (honey/ketchup like), and it continued to increase with temperature, which made processing difficult. Hence, a new series of silane endcapped polyaspartimide- based polymers were synthesized [10]. To increase material toughness/strength of these systems, as well as to impart shape memory capabilities, the silane endcaps were chemically cross-linked to create siloxane moieties throughout the polymeric system generating a thermosetting material with varying cross-link densities resulting in "tunable" glass transition temperatures. These materials offer elevated glass transitions accompanied with the desired ease of processability and resin work times. In addition, the generated materials maintain the cast shape with minimal shrinkage during the cure cycle.

However SMPs, in general, exhibit low strength and stiffness, which limits their use for many advanced applications. The low stiffness of SMPs produces only a small recovery force in the temperature change process. Thus, incorporation of reinforcing fillers has been investigated [11-19] in order to improve the mechanical properties and to diversify the applications of SMPs. For this study, the selected SMP resin [10] was hand-impregnated with IM7 uni-weave carbon fabric to fabricate six-ply composites. Both C-scan and optical microscopy techniques were utilized to determine the quality of the panels fabricated. The thermo-mechanical properties of the SMP resin and composite were measured using Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) and under 3-point flexure loading. In addition, the shape memory cycle with free recovery was conducted on the SMP resin and composites. The properties of the SMP resin and composites were characterized in both the glassy and rubbery regions, while their shape memory behavior was

analyzed under multiple thermomechanical cycles to analyze fatigue effects.

2 Experimental Methods

2.1 Resin Synthesis

All polymeric materials generated were synthesized using 4-4'-bismaleimidodiphenylmethane, Jeffamine D-400 (BMI-JA-400), and (3-Aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane. The trimethoxysilane moiety was chemically cross-linked with the addition of water yielding methanol as a byproduct and a cross-linking network of siloxane bonds. The molar amounts were varied between the Jeffamine D-400 and (3-Aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane to maintain stoichiometry with 4-4'-bismaleimidodiphenylmethane. This variation allowed for different cross-link densities to be achieved. Dimethylacetamide (DMAC) was incorporated to aid the cross-linking agent (water) to go into solution, as well as to help propagate the siloxane bond formation. Table 1 summarizes the composition of the various resins formulated for the study. Note that the percent listed in Table 1 is the molar percentage. For brevity, we will refer to the mixture of the BMI, JA 400, THF and the Endcap ((3-Aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane) as Part A, and a mixture of water and DMAC as Part B for the remainder of the paper.

Table 1: Summary of resin formulations

Formulas	Part A				Part B	
	BMI	JA400	THF	Endcap	Water	DMAC
BMI-JA-400-Si-80/20	5g	4.8g (80%)	9.72g	1.0g (20%)	0.251g	1.08g
BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30	5g	4.2g (70%)	9.63g	1.5g (30%)	0.377g	1.07g
BMI-JA-400-Si-60/40	5g	3.6g (60%)	9.54g	2.0g (40%)	0.503g	1.06g

Thermal analysis was done [10] to evaluate the developed SMP resin for composite processing feasibility. Based on these results, BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 was identified as possible candidate SMP resin for making composites. All the results reported in the remainder of this study are therefore limited to BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 as the initial choice of SMP resin. A post-cure for the SMP resin was subsequently developed [10] by monitoring the thermal stability of the material over a range of temperatures. The dynamic properties of the post-cured resin were investigated using DMA. The

$\tan(\delta)$ peak was used to define the T_g of the resin, which was estimated as $\sim 117^\circ\text{C}$. However, the $\tan(\delta)$ peak had a very broad distribution. The work to further narrow the distribution and optimize the T_g is currently being explored by considering several different combinations of post-cure time and temperature, and the results will be reported in a future publication.

2.2 Composite Processing

The resin consists of Part A and Part B (see Table 1) which were mixed at room temperature (RT) for 30 min to obtain a homogeneous solution. IM7 carbon fabric was hand-impregnated with the resin solution to make a prepreg. During prepregging, each ply was degassed for 2-3 minutes at room temperature with partial vacuum to pull off the solvent. Six plies of 6" x 6" impregnated fabric were stacked on top of each other for a target 30-35% fiber volume content in the laminate. The prepreg was then bagged and cured in an autoclave at 100 psi, followed with a 2 hr postcure at 200°C .

2.3 Thermo-Mechanical and Shape Memory Behavior

The thermo-mechanical performance of SMP resin and composites was examined under three-point bending using ASTM D790. A support span-to-depth ratio of 16:1 was used. The composite test specimens were cut perpendicular to the fiber direction. Flexural testing was conducted on unconditioned specimens at room (25°C) and at elevated (150°C) temperatures in order to evaluate the glassy and rubbery state modulus, flexural strength, and strain-to-failure. This testing is required to establish the useful design space for the SMP resin and composites.

Shape memory cycles were conducted in order to correlate the shape memory properties and performance of the SMP resin and composite materials. One shape memory cycle consists of recording the original shape of the sample with a digital camera, heating the sample to its high temperature state, folding the sample around a custom tooling to give it an $\sim 90^\circ$ bend, cooling the sample in the tooling to lock in the bent shape, and finally, free recovery in an MTS 651 environmental chamber with an optical window for making observations inside the chamber. A digital camera was used to record time lapse pictures of the sample during the free recovery portion of the shape

memory cycle. The temperature and time were also recorded automatically to match each photo taken. The digital images were post-processed to measure the degree of bend left in the sample vs. temperature (and time) as it unfolded during this recovery period. To evaluate the fatigue effect on the shape memory behavior, the free recovery cycle was performed a minimum of five times for each sample tested.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Resin Formulation and Characterization

We have now been able to successfully scale up to 200g mixture for making prepreg and neat resin plaques. Recent efforts were directed towards reducing the solvent content in the SMP resin when generating these materials. The reduction in solvent has reduced the time needed to synthesize these materials by nearly one-half and has resulted in development of the capability to cast “scale-up” polymeric films within minutes of initial reaction. This allows the actual film to cure once it has been cast at faster cure rates. Care has to be taken not to increase the resin viscosity upon the remove of the solvent to the point that processability becomes difficult. Fig. 1 is a picture of BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 resin plaque.

Fig. 1. Picture of BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 resin plaque

Fig. 2 illustrates the potential shape memory capabilities of BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 resin utilizing a rectangular strip (151 mm long, 38 mm wide and 2.6 mm thick). The polymer was easily deformed into a rolled/cylindrical shape at 160°C (above its T_g) and fixed into this temporary shape, when cooled back down to room temperature. The polymer qualitatively shows high toughness in both the glassy and rubbery states. Upon reheating to 160°C (again above the T_g), the material returned to the original form within 90s of thermal exposure. Time stamps are placed on each photograph in Fig. 2 in relation to shape memory recovery time when reheated above the material’s T_g .

Fig. 2. Free recovery of BMI-JA-400-Si-70/30 SMP resin on reheating to 160°C

3.2 Composite Fabrication and Characterization

Several 6” x 6” SMP composite panels were fabricated using both plain-weave and uni-weave carbon fabric. Panels were cured in the autoclave with 100 psi and vacuum pressure. Fig. 3 shows the C-scan and optical micrographs of selected regions of the cross-section of a plain-weave composite panel with a target fiber volume of 35%. As seen in Fig. 3, the composite panel was well consolidated with little or no voids. The photomicrographs show that there were no obvious quality differences between the white and red area versus the yellow and brown area in the C-scan. It was observed that there was more resin rich areas observed in the yellow and brownish regions which caused the density to slightly change in the C-scan signal.

Fig. 3. C-scan image and photomicrographs of two different locations in panel # 3 containing 35% fiber volume with an average panel thickness of 1.58mm

Fig. 4 illustrates the potential shape memory capabilities of a unidirectional SMP composite utilizing a rectangular strip (66 mm long, 19 mm wide and 2.5 mm thick). The laminate (cut perpendicular to the fiber direction) was easily deformed into a $\sim 90^\circ$ bend at 160°C (above its T_g) and fixed into this temporary shape, when cooled back down to room temperature. Upon reheating to 160°C (again above the T_g), the composite returned to the original form within 30s of thermal exposure. Time stamps are placed on each photograph in Fig. 4 in relation to shape memory recovery time when reheated above the materials T_g . These results demonstrate that the SMP composites fabricated in this study have the potential to return to their original shape and display shape-memory effects.

3.3 Bending Behavior

Figs. 5 and 6 are the load-displacement response of SMP resin and unidirectional composite, respectively, under 3-point bending at room temperature. The specimen was deflected until rupture occurred in the outer surface of the test specimen or until a maximum strain of $\sim 5.0\%$ was reached (at which point no further deflection was possible as the specimen came in contact with the surface). Prior to testing, both the SMP resin and composite panels were post-cured for 2 hr. at 200°C . The composite test specimens were cut perpendicular to the fiber direction. The experimental data shows little scatter for the five different resin and composite specimens that were tested. After an initial elastic response, the SMP resin undergoes yielding with only a small change in the load beyond the maximum attained, whereas, the composite specimens break before yielding, as

indicated by the sharp load drop in Fig. 6. As expected, the initial slope of the load-displacement response is larger for the composite in comparison to the neat resin specimen. Figs. 7 and 8 are the load-displacement response of SMP resin and unidirectional composite, respectively, at elevated temperature (150°C). Unlike the room temperature response which had a significant linear region prior to yielding, the SMP resin does not exhibit any linear region at elevated temperature. Also, there is a large scatter in the rubbery response for the SMP resin at the resulting smaller load levels. On the other hand, the unidirectional composite exhibits some limited yielding at 150°C , prior to failure.

Fig. 4. Free recovery of a unidirectional SMP composite on reheating to 160°C

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Fig. 5. Load-displacement response of SMP resin under 3-point bending at 25°C

Fig. 6. Load-displacement response of unidirectional SMP composite under 3-point bending at 25°C

Fig. 7. Load-displacement response of SMP resin under 3-point bending at 150°C

Fig. 8. Load-displacement response of unidirectional SMP composite under 3-point bending at 150°C

Table 2 compares the flexural response of SMP resin and composite at room (25°C) and at elevated temperature (150°C). As expected, there is a significant decrease in stiffness of the SMP resin and composite when tested at the elevated temperature. Further, stiffening the resin with carbon fiber leads to some modest improvement in modulus and the maximum stress attained by the SMP composite, while the composite strain at maximum stress is reduced by the constraining fibers.

Table 2: Flexural response of SMP resin and composites at room and elevated temperatures

Test Specimen	Temp °C	Max Stress, Ksi	Modulus Msi	Strain @ max stress, %
SMP resin	25	9.44	0.26	7.45
SMP resin	150	0.97	0.01	5.97
SMP composite	25	13.20	0.54	4.03
SMP composite	150	2.90	0.13	4.52

Fig. 9 shows examples of digital images taken at different stages of the shape memory cycle as a function of the test temperature. Fig. 9a is the original configuration of the specimen at room temperature. Fig. 9b is the deformed configuration of the specimen in the constrained position at 150°C. Fig. 9c is the fixed position of the specimen obtained by constrained cooling to room temperature from the locked position in Fig. 9b and subsequent release of constraint. Figs. 9d – 9i reveal that the specimen

returns back close to its original flat shape with increase of temperature during free recovery.

Fig. 9. Digital images showing different stages of shape memory cycle as function of temperature

Figs. 10 and 11 show the measurement of bend angle obtained during free recovery from the digital images similar to that shown in Fig. 9 under repeated shape memory cycles for the SMP resin and composite, respectively. Fig. 10 shows that the neat resin undergoes majority of the recovery between 60°C and 120°C, and heating it further to 150°C with a short hold at that temperature does not result in additional recovery. Moreover, there is little change in the recovery behavior of the SMP resin under repeated fatigue loading. On the other hand, Fig. 11 shows that the unidirectional composite begins to recover almost immediately when heated from room temperature, and continues to recover at temperature values far beyond the glass transition temperature of the composite. Further, the recovery of the composite continues with the short 5 min hold at the maximum temperature of 150°C. We further noted that the elevated temperature deformation of the composite became easier with repeated cycling, as angle closer to the desired 90° became possible without fear of breaking the composite during bending. Also, Fig. 11 shows that the free recovery response of the composite is smoother (as indicated by the curve fit through the data points) beyond the second shape memory cycle, and the behavior changes little with further cycling.

Fig. 10. Bend angle measurement with free recovery temperature as a function of number of cycles for SMP resin

Fig. 11. Bend angle measurement with free recovery temperature as a function of number of cycles for SMP composite

Fig. 12 is a comparison of the free recovery behavior of the neat resin and unidirectional composite for cycles 1 and 5. The comparison clearly shows that although the composite begins to recover at a lower temperature, the rate of recovery for the composite with increasing temperature is smaller in relation to the resin, and that the composite continues to recover at temperatures far beyond its glass transition temperature. We further observe in Fig. 12 that the neat SMP resin generally undergoes larger recovery in comparison to the composite.

Fig. 12. Comparison of bend angle measurement with free recovery temperature for SMP resin and composite

By definition, the shape fixing parameter is a measure of how well the material locks in its deformed shape from the elevated temperature. For an ideal shape memory material, the deformed state is exactly retained on release of the constraint following cooling to room temperature. However, in reality, some shape memory materials only achieve a state close to their deformed shape. For this study, the shape fixity R_f is defined as the ratio between the angle immediately after unloading (see Fig. 9c) to the locked-in angle of deformation (see Fig. 9b). On the other hand, the shape recovery parameter is a measure of how closely the material returns to the original shape in the shape memory cycle. Under bending, the linear shape recovery ratio R_r is defined as a function of the final angle (see Fig. 9i) following recovery and the initial angle (see Fig. 9a) before the shape memory cycle. These parameters are used to quantitatively compare the SMPs and their composites in the current research.

Table 3 provides a listing of the shape fixity and shape recovery for both neat resin and composite as a function of the fatigue cycle. As seen in Table 3, the SMP resin has excellent fixity (>95%) and almost complete recovery (>99%). In comparison to neat resin, the composite has lower fixity (>84%) and recovery (>94%) values. We also note that there is little change in both the shape fixity and shape recovery of neat SMP resin with fatigue cycling,

while the fixity is lower for the composite and recovery is seen to improve after the second cycle and changes little beyond that cycle for the SMP composite.

Table 3: Shape fixity and free recovery of SMP resin and composites as a function of fatigue cycle

Cycle #	Shape Fixity, %		Shape Recovery, %	
	Resin	Composite	Resin	Composite
1	98.2	83.5	100	93.8
2	98.3	89.7	99.9	98.2
3	96.7	84.3	100.5	99.2
4	95.1	88.6	100	98.9
5	98.9	86.3	99.4	100.1

Summary

In this work, we have discussed a new tailorable, high temperature SMP resin that can be readily processed to be incorporated into a composite matrix. Both neat resin and unidirectional laminates were fabricated and their glassy and rubbery responses characterized in bending. The shape memory behavior was analyzed under multiple temperature/deformation cycles to evaluate the fatigue effects. Results demonstrate that we have successfully developed SMP resin and composites with high T_g close to the desired value of 121°C, good shape fixity (>84%) and near complete recovery (> 94%).

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